

Study of lipid involvement in breast cancer by using vibrational imaging on tissue samples from normal and obese patients

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Abstract

Breast cancer has become the most diagnosed cancer globally, replacing lung cancer in 2020, with 2.3 million new cases and an estimated death of 685000 women. It is predicted that by the year of 2040 there would be an increase to around 3 million new cases and 1 million deaths worldwide. This calls for techniques for better and faster diagnosis, and in understanding the different biomarkers and the resulting metabolic alterations aiding the development and progression of the tumour. Obesity is associated with metabolic alterations that have shown to increase the risk of cancer and worsen its prognosis. It is associated with dysfunction of adipose tissue that alter the lipid metabolism resulting in excessive accumulation of adipose tissue at sites other than where they are classically found. Tumour cells depend on their microenvironment for nutrients, oxygen and for proliferation. The tumor microenvironment in breast cancer constitutes adipocytes, fibroblasts, endothelial cells, immune cells, and components of the extracellular matrix. The effects of adipocytes on the tumor prognosis are predominant as the breast is composed of abundant fatty tissue. Hence it is important to investigate these effects on molecular levels for understanding the communication between the adipocytes and the tumoral cells which is supporting the proliferation of the cancer.

The current diagnostic technique of cancer includes a three step procedure including imaging (such as MRI, Ultrasound imaging), clinical examination and histopathological assessment of biopsy sample if a lesion is suspected to be malignant. However, histopathological assessment observes the morphologic abnormalities in the sample sections and is limited to provide information on the biochemical alterations likely to occur within the tissue even before the morphology is modified. Vibrational spectroscopy has demonstrated its potential to provide diagnostic information. Additionally, vibrational spectroscopy can facilitate the prediction of the biochemical progression for different diseases in a rapid non-destructive manner. Raman spectroscopy is an inelastic scattering process which has incredible potential in biological sample analysis. This technique is capable of rendering information on the vibrational modes of molecules, thus giving access to the biochemical information needed about the sample of interest. Raman spectroscopy is also less time consuming compared to conventional methods of tissue analysis, because the hassle of sample preparation is minimum or not required.

The goal of this project is to study the alterations of lipid metabolic pathways in the tumour microenvironment and the impact of obesity in development and progression of breast cancer using vibrational spectroscopy. The tissue samples were collected from patients with body mass indices falling into the category of obese and normal. The samples were sectioned in frozen condition without any other sample preparations. The first experiments were carried out by using infra-red (IR) imaging to verify the structural integrity of the whole tissue sections and to identify the regions of interest within each section corresponding to the invasive front of the tumour. The imaging was carried out using Spotlight™ IR microscope (Perkin Elmer) and the IR images were then processed using Extended Multiplicative Scatter Correction and K-means clustering.

When the sample sections pass the structural quality check, selected regions associated with the tumoral invasive front were subjected to mapping using Raman imaging (LabRAM HR Evolution/ LabRAM Soleil (Horiba Scientific)) to perform a finer molecular and structural characterization of lipid content. Indeed, Raman scattering permits to access information related to molecular information of lipid such as their unsaturation level or their structural organization at the macromolecular level. The spectral data are analyzed by considering the body mass index of the patients. This analysis by spontaneous Raman spectroscopy will be also done to identify precise wavenumbers associated with the different lipid classes, permitting subsequently to probe SRS (Stimulating Raman Scattering) imaging of the sample sections and hence to investigate and quantify the molecular heterogeneity between the patients' samples. Furthermore, the tissue samples will be subjected to investigation with other imaging modalities such as coherent anti-stokes Raman scattering (CARS) imaging, Second harmonic generation (SHG) imaging, fluorescence imaging, multiphoton microscopy, polarimetric imaging, optical coherence tomography to investigate the global environment of the tumor and to see in which extent this tumor environment is different between normal and obese patients.